

Table S1. Tree deployment zones in the Pacific Northwest. Species are listed as their USDA plant symbol (USDA PLANTS Database).

Abbreviation	Zone coverage	Organization*	Year	Species [†]	Data source	References
(a) Ecological zone sets						
BEC	British Columbia	BCMof	2021	All (generic)	Ministry of Forests - Forest Analysis and Inventory. (2021). <i>BEC Map (version 12)</i> . Retrieved from https://catalogue.data.gov.bc.ca/dataset/bec-map	Meidinger and Pojar (1991)
EPA4	EPA Level IV Ecoregions	EPA	1986	All (generic)	United States Environmental Protection Agency. <i>US Level IV Ecoregions</i> . Retrieved from https://www.epa.gov/eco-research/level-iii-and-iv-ecoregions-continental-united-states	Omernik and Gallant (1986)
(b) Geographic zone sets						
CA	California	USFS	1970	All (generic)	Fire and Resource Assessment Program (Calif.). <i>California Tree Seed Zones Map</i> . Retrieved from https://maps.princeton.edu/catalog/stanford-sg575tf7838	Buck et al. (1970)
ID/MT	Idaho, E. Washington, W. Montana	IETIC	2020	All (generic)	Developed for this paper	

OR96	Oregon	ODF	1996	ABAM, ABCO, ABGR, ABMAS, ABPR, ALRU2, CADE27, CANO9, CHLA, PICO, PICOC, PIEN, PIJE, PILA, PIMO3, PIPO, PISI, POBAT, PSME, TABR2, THPL, TSHE, and 10 generic zones [‡]	Oregon Department of Forestry. <i>Seed Zones</i> . Retrieved from https://www.oregon.gov/ODF/aboutODF/Pages/MapsData.aspx	Sorensen (1979); Randall (1996)
OR66	Oregon	WFTSC	1966	All (generic)	Vicky Erickson, USFS Region 6 Geneticist	Randall (1996)
WA66	Washington	WFTSC	1966	All (generic)	Vicky Erickson, USFS Region 6 Geneticist	Randall (1996)
WA02	Washington	WDNR	2002	ABAM, ABGR, ABPR, ALRU2, CANO9, LAOC, PICO, PIEN, PIMO3, PIPO, PISI, POBAT, PSME, TABR2, THPL, and TSHE [‡]	Vicky Erickson, USFS Region 6 Geneticist	Randall and Berrang (2002)

*BCMoF is British Columbia Ministry of Forests, EPA is U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, IETIC is Inland Empire Tree Improvement Cooperative, ODF is Oregon Department of Forestry, USFS is United States Forest Service, WFTSC is Western Forest Tree Seed Council, and WDNR is Washington Department of Natural Resources.

[†]ABAM is Pacific silver fir, ABCO is white fir, ABGR is grand fir, ABMAS is Shasta fir, ABPR is noble fir, ALRU2 is red alder, CADE27 is incense-cedar, CANO9 is Alaska yellow cedar, CHLA is Port-Orford-cedar, LAOC is western larch, PICO is lodgepole pine, PICOC is shore pine, PIEN is Engelmann spruce, PIJE is Jeffrey pine, PILA is sugar pine, PIMO3 is western white pine, PIPO is ponderosa pine, PISI is Sitka spruce, POBAT is black cottonwood, PSME is Douglas-fir, TABR2 is Pacific yew, THPL is western redcedar, TSHE is western hemlock, and TSME is mountain hemlock.

[‡]For OR96 and WA02, only species-specific zones for which shapefiles existed were analyzed. This resulted in five species-specific zones being analyzed for OR96 and WA02.